

present (it is assumed for simplicity of treatment that concentration = activity).

$[A]$ = concentration of free ligand.

C_M = total concentration of all metal species.

The values of $\bar{n}$ were plotted against the corresponding values of pA and the values of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 correspond to $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively.

The refined values of $\bar{n}$ were then calculated using Bjerrum's splitting (spreading)⁵ factor X for each corresponding value of A . The final values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ may then be obtained from the plots of pA and $\bar{n}$ (refined) as the values of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values of formation constants are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Metal ion	$t=30 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$		
	$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$	$\log \beta$
Mn^{2+}	5.78	3.10	8.88
Co^{2+}	5.97	3.95	9.92
Ni^{2+}	6.00	4.57	10.57
UO_2^{2+}	6.86	4.84	11.70

A perusal of results shows that formation constants of the complexes are increasing in the order $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. The order of stability follows Irving-William Rule⁶.

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Formation Constants of the Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-2',6'-Diethylaniline with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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LITERATURE survey indicates that no systematic study of the stabilities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-diethylaniline with bivalent metal ions appears to have been carried out.

In the present communication the dissociation constants of the reagent and successive stability constants of a few of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-diethylaniline was synthesised by dissolving 10 gms of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde in absolute ethanol and to this was added equimolar quantity of 2,6-diethylaniline. The mixture was refluxed for about one hour on water bath and then was allowed to cool when solid separated out which was removed by filtration. The product was repeatedly crystallised to get analytically pure compound (observed m.p. 77°).

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. analytical grade except the perchloric acid which was of E. Merck grade.

The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in our earlier recent communication².

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic 'OH' group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The reagent formation curve extends over a range $0.39 < \bar{n}_A < 1.55$ and is wavelike indicating the formation of the species HL and H_2^+L in steps, separable. The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H were determined from half integral points at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5 respectively.

The metal-ligand stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for the metal ions studied were determined

from their respective formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria, which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and $\bar{n}=1.5$ respectively.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Cations	$t=25^{\circ}\text{C}$		$\mu=0.1M$				
	H^+	UO_2^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
$\log K_1$	9.90	9.25	8.77	5.87	5.45	5.97	4.07
$\log K_2$	2.48	7.50	—	—	—	—	—

The order of stability of bivalent metal chelates studied was

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-3'-Methoxyaniline with Some Divalent Metal Ions

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IN continuation of our earlier studies on the complexes of Schiff bases we report here the stability constants of Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mg(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-methoxyaniline determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

pH measurements were carried out on a Corning model 12, precision research pH meter equipped

with wide range glass and calomel electrodes. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale on which changes in pH can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit.

The ligand was synthesised and repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure sample². The dioxane used was purified by the method described by Vogel³. Distilled water redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was a 75 : 25 per cent (v/v) dioxane-water mixture in which the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M NaClO_4 . The preparation and standardisation of metal solutions together with details of the potentiometric titrations are the same as have been reported in an earlier communication⁴. The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti was applied to determine the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL .

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic 'OH' group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, Y , the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves using (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values were plotted. The formation curve extends over a range $0.3 < \bar{n}_A < 1.64$ and is wavelike. The value of $pK_1^H = 9.70$ was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ while that of $pK_2^H = 3.04$ was obtained at $\bar{n}_A = 1.5$.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) $\bar{n}$ and pL values were evaluated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria. From these curves the values of stability constants, $\log K_1$ which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n}=0.5$ were computed. These were: 8.90, 5.70, 5.56, 5.46 and 3.82 for the respective metals and are in agreement with the Irving and Williams order⁵ viz. $\text{Cu} > \text{Zn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Mg}$.

There is a relatively large difference between the $\log K_1$ values for the copper chelate and those for the chelates of other metals. The higher stability of the copper chelate may be due to the formation of a square-planar complex. The $\log K_1$ value for zinc is not much greater than that of nickel; $M-L\pi$ interaction between the π -orbitals of zinc and the ligand is therefore negligible.